

2-Acetylpyridine-2-aminobenzophenone-2-furoylhydrazone Complexes with 3d-Metal Ions : A Magnetic and Spectral Study

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Schiff base complexes¹ have been found effective catalysts for the epoxidation of various olefins. The catalytic activity has been correlated with the structure of the Schiff base, substituent groups on the Schiff base and the redox potential of the metal ion. In view of the above facts and our interest in the coordination chemistry of the heteroaroyl Schiff bases, some bivalent 3d-metal complexes of the title hydrazone have been prepared.

Results and Discussion

Two types of complexes having the neutral (Hapabfh) and the deprotonated (apabfh) hydrazone have been isolated (Table 1). The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but are slightly or fairly soluble in DMF and DMSO. The complexes are non-electrolytes in DMF solution.

In the addition compounds, amide-I and -II bands (Table 2) shift to lower frequencies suggesting coordination through the carbonyl oxygen. The disappearance of amide-I and amide-II bands and the appearance of new bands characteristic of ν_{NCO^-} in the spectra of the apabfh complexes, show bonding through the imidolate oxygen which is further supported by the absence of anions and 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry. In all complexes except 1, shifting of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ to lower frequencies, broadening and weakening of the intensity of the band(s) suggest bonding through the nitrogen of one of the C=N moieties. However, the shift of $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ to higher frequency is commensurate with involvement of the hydrazone nitrogen. The pyridine ring vibrations² at 615 and 405 cm^{-1} in Hapabfh are observed at 625–640 and 420–435 cm^{-1} in the apabfh complexes except 7 indicating interaction of pyridine nitrogen to the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND GENERAL BEHAVIOUR OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Compd./ (Colour)	M.p. °C	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)					Mol. cond. $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	
			Metal	N ₂ H ₄	Cl/SO ₄	C	H			N
1	VO(Hapabfh) ₂ SO ₄ (Light green)	152–55 ^a	5.3	–	9.5	61.5	4.2	11.2	11.5	1.74
			(5.2)	–	9.8	61.3	4.1	11.4)		
2	Mn(Hapabfh) ₂ Cl ₂ (Brown)	121–25 ^a	5.5	6.7	7.4	63.6	4.2	11.7	19.4	5.98
			(5.8)	6.8	7.5	63.7	4.3	11.9)		
3	Co(Hapabfh) ₂ Cl ₂ (Brown)	116–18 ^a	6.0	6.6	7.3	63.3	4.2	11.7	20.4	4.88
			(6.2)	6.8	7.5	63.4	4.2	11.8)		
4	Ni(Hapabfh) ₂ Cl ₂ (Orange-brown)	126–27 ^a	5.9	6.7	7.2	63.1	4.1	11.6	19.9	2.86
			(6.2)	6.8	7.5	63.4	4.2	11.8)		
5	Cu(Hapabfh) ₂ Cl ₂ (Green)	245–47	6.8	–	7.2	62.8	4.3	11.9	22.8	1.87
			(6.7)	–	7.5	63.1	4.2	11.8)		
6	Zn(Hapabfh) ₂ Cl ₂ (Yellow)	212–14 ^a	6.8	6.7	7.4	63.1	4.3	11.7	8.2	Diamag.
			(6.9)	6.7	7.5	63.0	4.2	11.8)		
7	VO(apabfh) ₂ (Light green)	121–23	5.6	–	–	68.2	4.2	12.5	19.2	1.88
			(5.8)	–	–	68.1	4.3	12.7)		
8	Mn(apabfh) ₂ (Cream)	120–21	6.4	7.2	–	68.9	4.3	12.7	21.4	5.89
			(6.3)	7.4	–	69.1	4.4	12.9)		
9	Co(apabfh) ₂ (Brown)	126–28	6.6	7.2	–	68.6	4.4	12.6	24.5	4.83
			(6.8)	7.3	–	68.7	4.4	12.8)		
10	Ni(apabfh) ₂ (Orange-brown)	145–46	6.5	6.9	–	68.5	4.5	12.7	10.7	2.83
			(6.7)	7.3	–	68.8	4.4	12.8)		
11	Cu(apabfh) ₂ (Green)	> 350	6.9	–	–	68.2	4.3	12.9	7.4	2.14
			(7.2)	–	–	68.4	4.3	12.8)		
12	Zn(apabfh) ₂ (Yellow)	> 350	7.5	7.1	–	68.0	4.2	12.6	9.4	Diamag.
			(7.4)	7.3	–	68.2	4.3	12.7)		

^aDecomposition temperature.

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT IR BANDS (cm⁻¹) AND THEIR ASSIGNMENT

Compd no	Amide-I	Amide-II	VC=N	VN-N	VM-O	VM-N	VM-Cl
Hapabfh	1 680	1 540	1 625, 1 620	1 015	—	—	—
1	1 665	1 525	1 625, 1 620	1 015	370	—	—
2	1 670	1 520	1 620, 1 615	1 035	375	305	270
3	1 660	1 520	1 620, 1 615	1 030	360	310	275
4	1 665	1 515	1 620, 1 610	1 030	360	320	270
5	1 650	1 520	1 615, 1 610	1 025	370	320	265
6	1 670	1 525	1 620, 1 615	1 040	370	325	265
	VNCO—						
7	1 560	1 335	1 620, 1 610	1 030	375	300	—
8	1 565	1 330	1 615, 1 610	1 035	360	300	—
9	1 560	1 320	1 615, 1 610	1 035	365	310	—
10	1 560	1 320	1 620, 1 610	1 030	365	310	—
11	1 565	1 325	1 615, 1 610	1 025	365	310	—
12	1 555	1 340	1 620, 1 615	1 025	370	305	—

metal ion. The chelating nature of SO₄²⁻ in **1** is inferred from the appearance of bands at 985, 1 035, 1 130 and 1 235 cm⁻¹. A band at 980 cm⁻¹ in **7** may unequivocally be assigned to ν_{V=O}. The bands³ at 1 510, 860 and 715 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to ν_{C-O}, CH out-of-plane bending and characteristic ring vibration of furan ring in Hapabfh, remain unchanged in the spectra of the complexes suggesting that furan oxygen is not involved in bonding. The bands observed at 360–375, 300–320 and 265–275 cm⁻¹ in the complexes may tentatively be assigned to ν_{M-O}, ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-Cl} modes respectively.

Magnetic moment values of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes lie in the range reported for the octahedral complexes⁴. The μ_{eff} values of Cu^{II} and OV^{IV} complexes correspond to one and those of Mn^{II} complexes to five unpaired electrons.

The electronic spectra of the OV^{IV} complexes yield two bands at 12 640 and 16 920 cm⁻¹ for **1** and 10 775 and 15 150 cm⁻¹ for **7** assuming a square-pyramidal geometry⁵. The observed *d-d* bands at 9 615, 15 130 and 23 310 cm⁻¹ for **3**, 10 140, 17 890 and 23 310 cm⁻¹ for **9**, 10 881 and 18 655 cm⁻¹ for **4** and 12 210, 17 985 and 22 770 cm⁻¹ for **10** are indicative of their octahedral geometry⁶ which is also supported by ν₂/ν₁ values (1.71 for **4** and 1.47 for **10**) lying in the range reported for octahedrally coordinated Ni^{II}. A broad band observed at 12 345 cm⁻¹ for **5** and 13 405 cm⁻¹ for **11** are assigned on the basis of an octahedral geometry.

The magnetic parameters evaluated from esr spectrum

of **1** in DMF (at LNT) has the trend $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp} < g_e$ indicating presence of the unpaired electron in d_{xy} (b_{2g}^*) orbital. The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ for the complex **5** is consistent with occupation of unpaired electron in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital⁷ resulting from Z-out tetragonal distortion. The σ-bonding parameter is indicative of the appreciable amount of metal-ligand orbital overlap. The μ_{eff} value (1.70 B.M.) is evaluated⁷ for **1** using the relations,

$$g_{\parallel} = g_e - \frac{8\lambda}{\Delta(d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2})}, \mu_{\text{eff}} = \mu_s \left(1 - \frac{2\lambda}{\Delta}\right) \text{ and } g_{\parallel} \text{ (1.93),}$$

$$g_e \text{ (2.002 3) and } \Delta \text{ (16 920 cm}^{-1}\text{). The relations } g_{\parallel} = g_e - \frac{8\lambda}{\Delta(d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy})}, \mu_{\text{eff}} = \mu_s \left(1 - \frac{2\lambda}{\Delta}\right) \text{ and } g_{\parallel} \text{ (2.26), } g_e \text{ (2.002 3) and } \Delta \text{ (12 345 cm}^{-1}\text{) yield } \mu_{\text{eff}} \text{ value 1.84 B.M. for } \mathbf{5}. \text{ These values are in agreement with those obtained from the bulk magnetic susceptibility measurements.}$$

X-Ray powder lines observed in **6** and **12** have been indexed⁸ which yields the lattice parameters : $a = b = 16.86$ and $c = 15.49$ Å for **6** and $a = b = 12.91$ and $c = 20.00$ Å for **12**. These parameters indicate that the models of the complexes are packed in a tetragonal unit lattice.

Experimental

2-Acetylpyridine, 2-aminobenzophenone and 2-furoylhydrazine (Aldrich) were used as such.

Preparation of Hapabfh : 2-Acetylpyridine-2-aminobenzophenone-2-furoylhydrazone was prepared by refluxing a mixture of 2-acetylpyridine (1.2 ml, 1 mmol) and an

TABLE 3—ESR MAGNETIC AND BONDING PARAMETERS

Compd no	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	A_{\parallel} G	A_{\perp} G	A_{av} G	a^2/β^2
1	1 93	1 98	1 96	195 57	73 57	114 28	0 93
5	2 26	2 05	2 12	158 33	25 00	69 44	0 76

ethanolic solution (20 ml) of 2-aminobenzophenone-2-furoylhydrazone⁹ (3.05 g, 1 mmol) for 4 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from hot ethanol, (75%), m.p. 185–86° (Found : C, 73.2; H, 4.9; N, 13.5; N₂H₄, 7.7. C₂₅H₂₀N₄O₂ requires : C, 73.5; H, 4.9; N, 13.7; N₂H₄, 7.8%).

Preparation of complexes : M(Hapabfh)₂Cl₂ [M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}] were prepared by adding an ethanolic solution (10 ml) of the metal chloride (1 mmol) to a solution of the hydrazone (2 mmol) in the same solvent (20 ml) and refluxing the solution for ~1 h. VO-(Hapabfh)₂SO₄ was prepared similarly by taking a methanolic solution of vanadyl sulphate. The complexes which precipitated after reducing the volume and adding diethyl ether were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. M(apabfh)₂ [M = OV^{IV}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}] were synthesised by mixing an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the hydrazone (2 mmol) and an aqueous solution (10 ml) of the metal salt (1 mmol) and raising the pH of the solution to ~7 by adding 1 N NaOH solution. The reaction solution was digested on a water-bath for ~1 h to ensure the complete deprotonation of the Schiff base. The complexes were filtered and washed with water, ethanol and diethyl ether and dried under reduced pressure.

The complexes were analysed for metal, chloride, sulphate and hydrazine using literature procedures¹⁰. The equipment and methods employed regarding C, H, N determination and molar conductance (at 10⁻³ M in DMF), magnetic moment, ir, electronic, esr and X-ray powder diffraction measurements were the same as described earlier¹¹.

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